

Using Foundation Model Embeddings to Map Colorado’s Built Hazard Interface for Wildfire: A Case Study in Scale

Aleksander Berg^{*,**} and Stefan Leyk^{*,**}

^{*}Department of Geography, University of Colorado Boulder

^{**}Institute of Behavioral Science, University of Colorado Boulder

Abstract

The wildland urban interface (WUI) is a critical zone where the built environment is adjacent to or intermixed with flammable wildland vegetation and where highly destructive wildfires can occur. WUI areas are typically mapped using vegetation and built-environment thresholds. We instead use patch embeddings provided by the Clay foundation model to capture landscape configurations related to structure level wildfire exposure. We train a series of random forest models to test how different patch sizes of Clay earth embeddings represent the wildfire hazardscape for Colorado 2000-2020. We build a workflow using embeddings and property data to predict structure level wildfire exposure probabilities. Our tests reveal coarser embedding patches perform better in our models compared to fine embedding patch sizes, but embeddings regardless of patch size perform very well at capturing fire exposure landscapes. We then use the models to predict potential wildfire exposure probabilities statewide for all available structures. Our analysis concludes with a discussion of the spatial effects of embedding patch size and how they should be reflected upon in applied analysis.

Keywords: earth embeddings, geospatial foundation model, wildfire, wildland urban interface

1. Introduction

On December 30, 2021 the Marshall fire ignited in the grasslands abutting residential development in Boulder, Colorado. Driven by high winds and unseasonably dry conditions, the fire took hold over the built-fabric and became an urban conflagration fire jumping from structure to structure. In a matter of hours, over 1,000 homes were destroyed, two people killed, and many thousands of residents displaced (Dickinson et al., 2025). The climatological, vegetated, and built-environment conditions that led to the Marshall fire have parallels in other recent events such as California’s Camp Fire that leveled the town of Paradise, killing 85 people and destroying nearly 14,000 structures (Cal OES, 2025). These wildland conflagration fire events occur in a space termed the wildland ur-

Published in “Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Geospatial Artificial Intelligence (GeoAI 2026) – Oral Presentation Papers”, edited by Haosheng Huang and Nico Van de Weghe, GeoAI 2026, 3-6 June 2026, Ghent, Belgium.

This contribution underwent single-blind peer review based on the extended abstract.

ban interface (WUI) or the space where flammable wildland vegetation and the built-environment intermingle (Butler, 1974).

WUI communities are at heightened risk of wildfire exposure and destruction due to their spatial configuration. Growing evidence points to humans being the main driver of wildland fire ignition. Over 85% of fires from 2000 to 2017 can be attributed to human causes such as campfires, mechanical and electrical equipment malfunction, and arson (Short, 2017). Notably, these human drivers act faster and at a finer spatial scale than changes in the vegetated system, making them more difficult to monitor. Wildland fire is not just a ‘natural’ problem but one generated by common interactions in the socioenvironmental system. For example, the configuration of the built environment is driven by human and societal choices which in turn can put people and property in interaction with a potentially flammable vegetated environment. These complexities of the wildland-fire hazardscape present challenges due to factors such as climate change, vegetation regimes, social structures, and governance practices (Robinne et al., 2018).

To understand where these communities are, methodologies and maps have been created to represent the WUI at vast spatial and temporal intervals. At its core, a WUI map does two things: (1) distill the complex interaction that generates wildfire potential into a binary (or vastly simplified) classification, in the interface or out of the interface and (2) allow for the assessment of areas for planning and mitigation of fire exposure. A number of WUI mapping methodologies and data products have been developed to satisfy these needs, for example: Radeloff et al. (2018); Carlson et al. (2022) produced WUI maps for the contiguous United States, Schug et al. (2023) mapped the WUI globally, and Radeloff et al. (2018); Ren (2021); Berg et al. (2024) mapped the WUI through time at the state or national level. These methods take information about the vegetated environment (e.g., distance and density of wildland vegetation) and the built environment (e.g., location and density of structures) and classify areas based on those configurations. These maps present a useful summary of the communities that have the conditions to produce destructive urban conflagration fire events like what was seen during the Marshall and Camp Fires.

Unfortunately, the data characterizing the vegetated and built environments that make up the backbone of these WUI maps are demanding to create, can be limited in temporal extent, or rely on the aggregation of disparate administrative data. A clear path for advancing the ability of monitoring the environments that lead to destructive urban conflagration fires would be supported by streamlining the intensity of data preparation and processing to apply these models. New modeling paradigms such as geospatial foundation models may be able to overcome these critical limitations and enable rapid assessment of at risk places.

Geospatial foundation models (GeoFM) are a new breed of machine learning models trained on vast remote-sensed imagery and other spatial data with the explicit goal of being flexible to downstream tasks (Janowicz et al., 2025). Built upon the latest advances in artificial intelligence and imagery models (typically transformer architectures), GeoFMs are trained to pick up latent patterns on Earth’s surface that can then be useful for more specialized tasks downstream. This new class of models front-loads the computational expense of learning patterns on Earth to make downstream finetuning much more computationally efficient and less data intensive (Szwarcman et al., 2024; Bodnar et al., 2025; Brown et al., 2025). Not only can these foundation models be finetuned

directly to specific tasks, their pattern recognition capabilities can be leveraged by generating embeddings.

Embeddings are numerical representations pulled from inside a model that represents the patterns or semantics the model is ‘seeing’ (Boykis, 2023). In processing spatial data such as imagery, embeddings represent an abstraction of the image’s patterns in a more effective fashion that is more valuable than its original form (Yuan and McKee, 2022). Foundation models have now been used to generate embeddings using multi-modal spatial data on a global scale (Brown et al., 2025). These embeddings can be leveraged in downstream modeling tasks built upon classic machine learning algorithms such as random forest.

Our central goal with this work is to show how GeoFM earth embeddings can be integrated into a probabilistic modeling of structure level wildfire exposure in the wildland urban interface. We use the Clay Foundation model (Clay Foundation, 2024) to turn stable Landsat imagery composites into patch embeddings, which represent the patterns in an image, into a stack of vector values. We build a series of structure level fire exposure probability models for Colorado, United States using data over more than twenty years (2000-2024) of wildfire patterns, property assessor records and building footprints (FEMA, 2022), as well as patch level embeddings. To achieve our central goal and build this pipeline we identify two distinct questions about how foundation models represent landscape characteristics. First, what patch size of embeddings provides the best information about wildfire prone landscapes? Second, how can the fitness-for-use of GeoFM embeddings be assessed in applied domains?

2. Data and Methodology

This study was carried out for the state of Colorado, United States from 1990 to 2020. Colorado has seen large-scale housing development and numerous large, destructive, and costly wildfires (NIFC, 2020; Barbier and Gifford, 2025). Colorado and its environmental and socioeconomic complexity presents an opportunity to unlock new answers about the hazard problem by applying novel methodology using high resolution spatial data. Colorado is also well represented by many high-resolution datasets that capture relevant processes at fine spatial and temporal scales.

To summarize, for this work, we built a data workflow for extracting Clay GeoFM embeddings from Landsat composites. We examined five patch sizes of embeddings (240 m, 480 m, 960 m, 1920 m, 3840 m) and three temporal epochs (2000, 2010, and 2020). We joined these embeddings to property-level data and to then predict structure level wildfire exposure across patch sizes using a presence only random forest modeling scheme. We tested the efficacy of these models and mapped their results.

2.1. Data

Mapping the structure level probability of wildfire exposure requires three categories of data that capture dynamics across the domains of (1) fire, (2) structures, and (3) land cover. The integration and use of these data is visualized in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Flowchart of data flow, model training, and prediction.

Notes: The flowchart shows the workflow for the data processing, training of the model, and structure level exposure prediction. The figure is divided into four sections from top to bottom: ‘Inputs’ (showing the input data sources), ‘Embedding and Data Cleaning’ (showing the data cleaning and preparation), ‘Model Training’ (showing the exposure model training procedure), and ‘Model Prediction’ (showing the prediction and classification procedure). Three separate flows of data are shown by theme from left to right: ‘Building Data’ (containing the parcel and building footprint workflow), ‘Fire Data’ (containing the fire perimeter workflow), and ‘Landcover Data’ (containing the remote sensed imagery and embedding workflow).

First, wildland fire exposure data were provided in form of the 2024 version of the Fire Events Delineation (FIRED) dataset for the Conterminous United States and Alaska (Balch et al., 2020; Mahood et al., 2022). The FIRED polygon dataset of fire perimeters is generated using the Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) MCD64A1 fire burn product. *Second*, for structure-level attributes, we leveraged parcel level housing characteristics like locations of structures, property values, transaction data on property sales, and land use. These data were provided by the county tax-assessor data aggregator Parcel Atlas (now ReGrid) who take county tax records and harmonize and aggregate them into a nationally representative database. Building footprint data was provided by the Federal Emergency Management Agency’s USA Structures Dataset (2022). The USA Structures dataset is a regularly updated collection of all structures in the U.S. with more than 450 square feet building footprint area (FEMA, 2022; Yang et al., 2024). *Third*, to capture land cover, we extracted cloudless summertime (May 1st to September 30th) “leaf-on” (Jin et al., 2023) geometric median composites of Landsat 5 and 8 Collection 2 images from 1995-2020 using Google Earth Engine (Gorelick et al., 2017). We selected six bands pulled from both platforms representing the blue, green, red, near-infrared, and shortwave infrared (1 & 2) wavelengths. Imagery for this analysis are collated annual summertime leaf-on geometric median composites for the 5-years leading up to each of the three temporal epochs of 1990, 2010, and 2020. For example, the 2000 geometric median imagery composite is produced from images from 1995 to 1999.

2.2. Methodology

The methodology centers around a data generation procedure built upon three main analytical tasks: (1) foundation model embedding and data cleaning, (2) model training, and (3) prediction. The first task, foundation model embedding and data cleaning produced the analytical dataset for this project, particularly creating a set of embeddings from Landsat imagery using the Clay foundation model. The second task, model training, generated a set of predictive models of building-level potential wildland fire exposure. The third task, prediction, took the trained models and used it to classify Colorado’s wildfire prone built environments. These analytical steps are described separately in the following sections.

2.2.1. Creating a building level dataset

The main analytical units were based on individual structures generated through an integration procedure that combined the best known structure locations with detailed attribute information from the harmonized tax assessor database, Parcel Atlas. To create this dataset, we undertook a three-tiered integration scheme based on available data. First, where a USA Structure was present and the Parcel Atlas record flagged the property as built-up, we performed a within-spatial join for all properties within the parcel (1,938,132 structures were joined to 1,441,003 Parcel Atlas Records). Second, when a Parcel Atlas record flagged the property as built-up, but no USA Structure was present, we used the centroid of the parcel as the structure location (418,491 Parcel Atlas records were turned into structure locations). Third, buildings that remained un-joined were then joined to the nearest Parcel Atlas record within 100 m (191,683 structures of 294,386 un-joined structures were matched using the nearest join procedure, the rest omitted). The enhanced structures dataset contained 2,548,306 individual structure locations. These structures represent the 2020 epoch of Parcel Atlas data which cover 54 of the 64 counties of Colorado. A total of 1,606 structures were dropped from the remaining data due to missing a built year record. After dropping rows for

missing a built year, the final enhanced structures dataset contained 2,546,352 structures.

The enhanced structures dataset was then filtered into three temporal epochs (2000, 2010, and 2020) based on the built year contained in the Parcel Atlas dataset. The 2000 temporal epoch contains structures built on or before 2000 (1,978,438 structures), the 2010 temporal epoch contains structures built on or before 2010 (2,338,394 structures), and the 2020 temporal epoch contains structures built on or before 2020 (2,546,352 structures).

2.2.2. Foundation model embedding of Landsat imagery

Next, the land cover components of the analytical database were generated by converting remote sensed imagery into embeddings using a spatial foundation model. For this analysis, we leveraged the fully open source, non-profit created, Clay Foundation model (Clay Foundation, 2024). Clay is a 632 million parameter transformer model trained on 70 million image chips.

Clay v1.5 was used as a pattern extraction engine to pull embeddings from within the model. Embeddings are mathematical representations of the semantic relationships that exist in imagery or more simply they are abstractions of the landscape patterns seen in the imagery. As described, using Google Earth Engine's python package, we generated leaf-on geometric median composites for three temporal epochs: 2000, 2010, and 2020. Using the TorchGeo 'Grid Geo Sampler,' five sizes of image patches were created from the composites with a 50% area overlap between the patches: 240m (8 x 8 pixel), 480 m (16 x 16 pixel), 960 m (32 x 32 pixels), 1920 m (64 x 64 pixels), and 3840 m (128 x 128 pixels). The bands in these chips were normalized using means and standard deviations provided by Clay. Next, batches of these image patches were fed into the Clay foundation model. The resulting outputs were image patches each of which contained a set of 1024 embedding dimensions with varying patch sizes.

The five patch sizes of the foundation model embeddings were appended to the enhanced structure-level dataset already prepared using a nearest spatial join between the structure centroid and the centroid point of the nearest embedding patch. Due to the potential of multicollinearity and redundancy (Papazafeiropoulos et al., 2026) in the embeddings, we decided to reduce the dimensionality of the embeddings data joined to the enhanced structure dataset using a principal components analysis. For each embedding patch size, a number of components was selected that covered 90% of the variation in the embedding space. The embeddings were reduced from 1024 dimensions to 18 components for the 240 m embeddings, 148 components for the 480 m embeddings, 194 components for the 960 m embeddings, 141 components for the 1920 m embeddings, and 75 components for the 3840 m embeddings.

2.2.3. Creating the target variable

The target variable is a binary expression of exposed / not exposed to wildland fire. This binary variable was created by filtering the FIRED perimeters dataset to fires not in agricultural land. The remaining perimeters were given a 1 km buffer to represent the zone of highest potential ember travel and exposure (Mietkiewicz et al., 2020). The buffered FIRED perimeters were then split into three temporal epochs: 2000 to 2009, 2010 to 2019, and 2020 to 2024. These epochs were joined to the enhanced structures data of the same epoch. For example, the 2000 to 2009 FIRED perimeters were joined to the 2000 epoch of enhanced structures. Any structure joined to a FIRED

perimeter were flagged as ‘exposed’ and the remaining structures ‘not exposed.’

2.2.4. Model training and prediction

The predictive models of potential structure level wildfire exposure are derived in reference to methodology developed for presence only species distribution modeling where the spatial range of a species is predicted from a set of known locations of that species and a set of locations where it’s absent (Renner et al., 2015). Essentially, these models predict a binary outcome of where a species is present or absent, derived only from the locations where that species is spotted and their environmental context. The training dataset for a species distribution model is typically setup to include a set of ‘presence’ points where the species has been recorded and a random set of ‘background’ points where the species may be located but was not recorded.

We use the framework provided by presence-only models and the random forest machine learning algorithm to predict the types of structures that have the potential to be exposed to wildland fire based on the environmental (built and vegetated) conditions they are situated in. In a similar vein to species distributions presence-only models, we have a set of known location where structures have been exposed to wildland fire, these are our ‘presence’ points. We also have a set of structures that were not exposed to wildland fire but may or may not be in environments that are conducive to fire events, these are our ‘background’ points. The objective of our models is to capture the environmental conditions that lead to heightened wildland fire exposure of structures within Colorado.

First, to model the relative potential of fire exposure, we created a training dataset using the target variable described previously. 26,641 structures in all temporal epochs were flagged as exposed to wildland fire. We then randomly sampled an equal number of ‘background’ points (26,641) from the remaining structures in the dataset. The training dataset, totaling 53,282 is fully balanced with half the structures flagged as ‘exposed’ and half flagged as ‘not exposed’ covering all three temporal epochs of structure and exposure data. Five model-ready datasets included the target with a binary label of exposure and the features of land use of the structure, the built-year of the structure, and the components provided by each embedding patch size.

We performed a spatial block five-fold cross validation split (Roberts et al., 2017) of the training dataset to tune, train, and validate the model. We created a grid of 20 km blocks over the training dataset; the blocks were split randomly into five equal groups. The underlying points were then assigned their folds based on the blocks. The spatial block fold procedure overcomes significant spatial autocorrelation and memorization issues that can overstate model performance in the held out test fold (Roberts et al., 2017).

The model-ready and split data were used for hyperparameter tuning a random forest model for each embedding patch size. The hyperparameter tuning itself was conducted using the Optuna (Akiba et al., 2019) search procedure over 30 trials selecting for the model with the highest F1 score. Each of the resulting models were then calibrated using a spline calibration procedure (Brian, 2018) on the held-out fifth fold of data. The models then underwent an F2-optimization to choose the probability threshold that favors recall of the exposed ‘presence’ class in binary prediction. Lastly, the fifth fold of data were then used to perform a series of diagnostics and model fit checks. These trained, calibrated, and optimized models were each exported to a pickle

(.pkl) file for downstream prediction. The trained, calibrated, and optimized models were finally used to predict the relative probability of wildfire exposure using the 2020 epoch of structure data.

3. Results

Our by-patch size model training, prediction, and performance testing produced two sets of results: model optimization and performance and structure level predictions. We first present the results on optimization and performance across models. Then, we present a series of example maps of structure level predictions for the cities of Boulder, Aspen, and Fort Morgan in Colorado.

3.1. Model performance

The five calibrated models, shown in Table 1 have relatively high overall fit metrics with AUC-ROC values ranging from 0.77 (240 m model) to 0.89 (3840 m model). The two best performant models across AUC-ROC are the 3840 m model at 0.89 and the the 960 m model at 0.86. The 3840 m model performs best across other metrics as well, with an overall accuracy of 0.79 and an F1 score of 0.80. The 960 m model also performs quite well with an overall accuracy of 0.72 and and F1 score of 0.74. Due to the F2 optimization, the exposed class recall is higher than 0.95 for all models, trading off precision.

Table 1: Calibrated and F2 optimized model performance across embedding patch sizes

Patch Size	Threshold	Discrimination			Exposed class			
		AUC-ROC	AUPRC	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1	F2
240m	0.15	0.77	0.69	0.55	0.49	0.98	0.65	0.82
480m	0.16	0.80	0.73	0.60	0.52	0.97	0.68	0.83
960m	0.21	0.86	0.79	0.72	0.61	0.95	0.74	0.86
1920m	0.13	0.82	0.73	0.65	0.55	0.98	0.71	0.85
3840m	0.18	0.89	0.83	0.79	0.69	0.96	0.80	0.89

3.2. Example maps of structure level predictions

Figure 3 shows the calibrated structure-level relative probability values for all embedding patch sizes (240 m in top row and 3840 m in bottom row) for the three example locations of Boulder, Aspen, and Fort Morgan. Stepping through the patch sizes, the 240 m model shows Aspen with overall higher relative probabilities (0.53 on average) than Boulder (0.32 on average) or Fort Morgan (0.39 on average). The 480 m model holds this trend showing Aspen with overall higher relative probabilities (0.53 on average) than Boulder (0.30 on average) or Fort Morgan (0.29 on average). Likewise with the 960 m model (0.57 on average in Aspen, 0.19 on average in Boulder, and 0.17 on average in Fort Morgan), the 1920 m (0.62 on average in Aspen, 0.20 on average in Boulder, and 0.21 on average in Fort Morgan) model, and the 3840 m model (0.29 on average in Aspen, 0.06 on average in Boulder, and 0.07 on average in Fort Morgan).

While the relative probabilities highlight an expected pattern, the visual spatial distribution of probabilities across the five embedding patch sizes reveals important variation in what each model

Figure 2: Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curves for all embedding patch sizes

represents. A key result, is that while the predictions are occurring as references to the structure location, the importance of the patch embeddings in the predictions in essence makes the prediction scale roughly the size of the embedding patches themselves. You can see how this progresses from finer patches (240 m) to coarser ones (3840 m) in the block-like nature of the predictions. This indicates that the spatial context provided by the embeddings is being highly relied upon in the random forest models for prediction, regardless of the patch size.

These patches can be seen as contextual blocks, akin to that of a traditional scan statistic used in remote sensing or more classical GIScience workflows and can be perceived as summary estimates similar to resampling outcomes. The finest patch embeddings at 240 m are similar in size to a city block, the contextual window leads to a highly variable prediction regime (see the stippling effect across the patches). The 480 m patch embedding model shows similar spatial distributions across all three example locations, yet at a coarser analytical scale. The 960 m patch embedding model, the second highest performing model according to our model fit metrics, shows more spatial consistency and less local variation than the finer models. For example, the highest relative probability of fire exposure is situated at the edge of Boulder in areas abutting wildland vegetation.

Interestingly, the relative probability of fire exposure in the 960 m model drops considerably for Fort Morgan in comparison to the 240 m and 480 m models, indicating a better contextualization of the difference between agricultural vegetation and wildland vegetation. The 1920 m model continues this trend across the three example locations. Finally, the 3840 m model, our highest performing model across model fit metrics, shows fewer structures as high relative risk across all three example locations. The larger patch sizes visually seem to reduce the variation and identify very few structures that meet higher relative probability values. This can be seen clearly in the Aspen map (bottom row, middle column) where the center of town has lower relative probabilities than the edges, while all values show patterns of a square box the size of the embedding patch.

Figure 3: By-embedding patch size 2020 structure-level calibrated relative probability values for Aspen, Boulder, and Fort Morgan

4. Discussion

4.1. What patch size of embeddings provides the best information about wild-fire prone landscapes?

The model fit metrics and maps of relative probability estimates highlight that two models pull ahead of the rest. The 3840 m patch embedding model performs best across most metrics: calibrated and uncalibrated. Though, when visualizing the predictions made with the 3840 m model, a tradeoff is revealed: a large contextual window with limited variability over local specificity. These results show that the models tend to take on patterns related to the patch size of the embeddings even though the unit of analysis are structures with their exposed / not exposed label. The 3840 m model highlights a classic geographic problem, the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP) also known as the Openshaw effect (Openshaw and Taylor, 1979).

As is well known, the Openshaw effect simply indicates that the statistical (as well as the spatial) distribution of a process changes depending on the underlying spatial unit of analysis. Our results show that patch level embeddings are no different: as the spatial extent of the image patches fed into the Clay model change, the resulting embeddings change. Large patch size embeddings like the 3840 m patches represent a larger frame for the model to work with and can provide context about the environment at the scale coarser than the immediate neighborhood but do not reflect local variation well. Small patch size embeddings, such as the 240 m show less of a contextual window effect but are more spatially precise, potentially capturing local-level differences and inherent variation.

At first, our results appear to point to an unsatisfactory answer to our question of best model fit and performance measures. However, as is often the case, it depends. If we were to only aim at optimizing model performance, we would choose the 3840 m embeddings as our optimal patch size. The 3840 m model performed best with regards to pure model performance metrics, with a high AUC-ROC value, indicating a robust ability to differentiate between landscape types, regardless of the decision making threshold chosen. However,, qualitatively, the 3840 m model's coarse spatial scale has limited ability to effectively characterize the landscape and creates unspecific, coarser-than-neighborhood-level predictions.

If we were to instead add in our knowledge of the wildland fire process and balance the tradeoff between spatial granularity and model performance, we would possibly pick the 960 m embeddings as our optimal patch size. The 960 m models do still have a high AUC-ROC value, trailing only slightly behind the 3840 m model, but the significantly smaller patch size provide much needed geographic specificity and spatial variation that the 3840 m model cannot. The 960 m embeddings conform to the landscape, yet still provide context beyond the structure. Additionally, the 960 m model happens to have a similar areal extent to the 500 m radius moving window used to produce maps of the wildland urban interface. Our results highlight the need to weight the benefits such as pure model performance against expert knowledge of the process of interest when choosing an embedding patch size.

4.2. Lessons Learned: How can GeoFM embeddings be used in applied domains?

Our results highlight that GeoFM earth embeddings are susceptible to the very same spatial aggregation effects and constraints that past analytical techniques fell victim to. The work here leads us to make a few suggestions for future work using earth embeddings for applied analysis.

(1) *garbage in, garbage out*: Choose data that matches the temporal and spatial scales of the process of study. Regardless of your downstream task, the input data matters and critically assessing if that data can represent the process of study is necessary. The high-dimensionality of embeddings cannot make up for poor resolution of input data nor a mismatch in temporality or general data quality issues.

(2) *distill*: Reduce the dimensionality of your embedding space to enhance generalization potential and help with multi-collinearity. We find Embedding dimensions are highly collinear and reduction of dimensionality helps with model performance. An added benefit of dimensionality reduction is a decreased storage demand and an increase in computation speed.

(3) *use standard machine learning workflows*: Embeddings fit nicely into standard workflows and can replace raw remote sensing imagery and derivatives such as land cover data. Embeddings can be used in simple models such as random forest with high efficacy. We note that one must be very careful of spatial memorization. Due to the high dimensionality our testing revealed that models can easily overfit and memorize individual embeddings instead of generalizing. Our solution was to implement a spatial block-fold cross validation where the test data was located in blocks spatially separated from the training data.

(4) *evaluate*: Choose a set of evaluation metrics that fit the process of study, we care about such as AUC-ROC for decision making evaluation, or the F2 score of the exposed class in order to favor recall of predictions of fire prone structures. We suggest calibrating models to accurately represent probabilities and optimize decision thresholds accordingly, if binary prediction is needed.

(5) *rinse and repeat*: Iteration across more than one embedding patch size may be needed to see what is best for your process of study. We suggest testing before settling on a single patch size and/or contextual outcome variable. Reflect qualitatively on what the model is predicting semantically (e.g., look at how the model highlights structures that were exposed to recent fire events nearby). The relative computational efficiency of producing embeddings and using simpler downstream models such as random forest allow for much more iteration and critical reflection.

Embeddings present a clear innovation in the space of applied spatial modeling. We find high levels of model performance and generalization from relatively simple data and model constructions. Our work here presents a testbed for modeling wildfire exposure but the lessons learned extend far beyond fire. Our hope is that GeoFM earth embeddings can be critically reflected upon as many of the typical fallacies of geographic data and analysis are ever present. GeoFM embeddings may have significant upsides, if used properly, and can be truly valuable in applied domains.

Acknowledgments

This research has been supported by the University of Colorado Boulder Institute of Behavioral Science's Graduate Student Summer Award Program and the Department of Geography's James A. & Jeanne B. DeSana Graduate Research Award. We thank Song Gao and the National Science Foundation for travel funding that made possible the presentation of this work at the 13th International Conference on Geographic Information Science. We are grateful for the thoughtful feedback from the participants of the 32nd International Cartographic Conference (ICC) and 13th International Conference on Geographic Information Science.

This research has also benefited from support by the University of Colorado Population Center (Project 2P2CHD066613) from the Eunice Kennedy Shriver National Institute on Child Health and Human Development [NICHD] and the NIA-funded Interdisciplinary Research Network on Rural Population Health and Aging (R24AG065159). The views expressed here do not necessarily reflect the official policies of the Department of Health and Human Services; nor does mention of trade names, commercial practices or organizations imply endorsement by the U.S. Government.

References

- Akiba, T., S. Sano, T. Yanase, T. Ohta, and M. Koyama (2019). Optuna: A next-generation hyperparameter optimization framework. In *Proceedings of the 25th ACM SIGKDD International Conference on Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining*.
- Balch, J. K., L. A. St. Denis, A. L. Mahood, N. P. Mietkiewicz, T. M. Williams, J. McGlinchy, and M. C. Cook (2020, October). FIRED (fire events delineation): An open, flexible algorithm and database of US fire events derived from the MODIS burned area product (2001–2019). *Remote Sens. (Basel)* 12(21), 3498.
- Barbier, E. and T. Gifford (2025, March). Battle scars: Trends in wildfire size and impact across colorado. Technical report, REDI Report.
- Berg, A. K., D. S. Connor, P. Kedron, and A. E. Frazier (2024, June). Remapping california’s wildland urban interface: A property-level time-space framework, 2000–2020. *Appl. Geogr.* 167, 103271.
- Bodnar, C., W. P. Bruinsma, A. Lucic, M. Stanley, A. Allen, J. Brandstetter, P. Garvan, M. Riechert, J. A. Weyn, H. Dong, J. K. Gupta, K. Thambiratnam, A. T. Archibald, C.-C. Wu, E. Heider, M. Welling, R. E. Turner, and P. Perdikaris (2025, May). A foundation model for the earth system. *Nature*, 1–8.
- Boykis, V. (2023). What are embeddings.
- Brian, L. (2018, September). Spline-based probability calibration. *arXiv [stat.ML]*.
- Brown, C. F., M. R. Kazmierski, V. J. Pasquarella, W. J. Rucklidge, M. Samsikova, C. Zhang, E. Shelhamer, E. Lahera, O. Wiles, S. Ilyushchenko, N. Gorelick, L. L. Zhang, S. Alj, E. Schechter, S. Askay, O. Guinan, R. Moore, A. Boukouvalas, and P. Kohli (2025, July). AlphaEarth foundations: An embedding field model for accurate and efficient global mapping from sparse label data. *arXiv [cs.CV]*.
- Butler, C. P. (1974). The urban/wildland fire interface. In *Proceedings of the Western States Section of the Combustion Institute*. Western States Section of the Combustion Institute.
- Cal OES (2025, November). 2018 camp fire after action report. Technical report, Governor’s Office of Emergency Services.
- Carlson, A. R., D. P. Helmers, T. J. Hawbaker, M. H. Mockrin, and V. C. Radeloff (2022, July). The wildland-urban interface in the united states based on 125 million building locations. *Ecol. Appl.* 32(5), e2597.
- Clay Foundation (2024). Clay.
- Dickinson, K., H. Walters, D. Crow, E. Albright, Rumbach, Rosenow, M. Kadota, N. Jeschke, Javernick-Will, and N. Gershon (2025). Colorado’s marshall fire: Recovery, mitigation, resilience through social equity lens. Technical report, Natural Hazards Center, University of Colorado Boulder.

- FEMA (2022). USA structures. <https://gis-fema.hub.arcgis.com/pages/usa-structures>. Accessed: 2022-6-21.
- Gorelick, N., M. Hancher, M. Dixon, S. Ilyushchenko, D. Thau, and R. Moore (2017). Google earth engine: Planetary-scale geospatial analysis for everyone. *Remote sensing of Environment* 202, 18–27.
- Janowicz, K., G. Mai, W. Huang, R. Zhu, N. Lao, and L. Cai (2025, September). GeoFM: how will geo-foundation models reshape spatial data science and GeoAI? *Geogr. Inf. Syst.* 39(9), 1849–1865.
- Jin, S., J. Dewitz, P. Danielson, B. Granneman, C. Costello, K. Smith, and Z. Zhu (2023, January). National land cover database 2019: A new strategy for creating clean leaf-on and leaf-off landsat composite images. *J Remote Sens* 3.
- Mahood, A. L., E. J. Lindrooth, M. C. Cook, and J. K. Balch (2022, July). Country-level fire perimeter datasets (2001-2021). *Sci. Data* 9(1), 458.
- Mietkiewicz, N., J. K. Balch, T. Schoennagel, S. Leyk, L. A. St. Denis, and B. A. Bradley (2020, September). In the line of fire: Consequences of human-ignited wildfires to homes in the U.S. (1992–2015). *Fire* 3(3), 50.
- NIFC (2020). Wildland fire summary and statistics annual report 2020. Technical report, National Interagency Coordination Center.
- Openshaw, S. and P. J. Taylor (1979). A million or so correlation coefficients : three experiments on the modifiable areal unit problem. *Statistical applications in the spatial sciences*, 127–144.
- Papazafeiropoulos, T., N. I. Bountos, N. Papadopoulos, and I. Papoutsis (2026, March). Hide and seek: Investigating redundancy in earth observation imagery. *arXiv [cs.CV]*.
- Radeloff, V. C., D. P. Helmers, H. A. Kramer, M. H. Mockrin, P. M. Alexandre, A. Bar-Massada, V. Butsic, T. J. Hawbaker, S. Martinuzzi, A. D. Syphard, and S. I. Stewart (2018, March). Rapid growth of the US wildland-urban interface raises wildfire risk. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 115(13), 3314–3319.
- Ren, Y. (2021). *Refining the Wildland-Urban Interface: Implications for Risk Exposure of the Built Environment for Colorado over 25 Years*. Ph. D. thesis, University of Colorado at Boulder, Boulder, Colorado, USA.
- Renner, I. W., J. Elith, A. Baddeley, W. Fithian, T. Hastie, S. J. Phillips, G. Popovic, and D. I. Warton (2015, April). Point process models for presence-only analysis. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 6(4), 366–379.
- Roberts, D. R., V. Bahn, S. Ciuti, M. S. Boyce, J. Elith, G. Guillera-Arroita, S. Hauenstein, J. J. Lahoz-Monfort, B. Schröder, W. Thuiller, D. I. Warton, B. A. Wintle, F. Hartig, and C. F. Dormann (2017, August). Cross-validation strategies for data with temporal, spatial, hierarchical, or phylogenetic structure. *Ecography (Cop.)* 40(8), 913–929.

- Robinne, F.-N., J. Burns, P. Kant, M. D. Flannigan, M. Kleine, B. de Groot, and M. Wotton (2018). Global fire challenges in a warming world. Technical Report Occasional paper No. 32, International Union of Forest Research Organizations.
- Schug, F., A. Bar-Massada, A. R. Carlson, H. Cox, T. J. Hawbaker, D. Helmers, P. Hostert, D. Kaim, N. K. Kasraee, S. Martinuzzi, M. H. Mockrin, K. A. Pfoch, and V. C. Radeloff (2023, September). The global wildland-urban interface. *Nature* 621(7977), 94–99.
- Short, K. C. (2017). Spatial wildfire occurrence data for the united states, 1992-2015 [fpa_fod_20170508] (4th edition). Title of the publication associated with this dataset: Forest Service Research Data Archive.
- Szwarcman, D., S. Roy, P. Fraccaro, P. E. Gislason, B. Blumenstiel, R. Ghosal, P. H. de Oliveira, J. L. d. S. Almeida, R. Sedona, Y. Kang, S. Chakraborty, S. Wang, C. Gomes, A. Kumar, M. Truong, D. Godwin, H. Lee, C.-Y. Hsu, A. A. Asanjan, B. Mujeci, D. Shidham, T. Keenan, P. Arevalo, W. Li, H. Alemohammad, P. Olofsson, C. Hain, R. Kennedy, B. Zadrozny, D. Bell, G. Cavallaro, C. Watson, M. Maskey, R. Ramachandran, and J. B. Moreno (2024, December). Prithvi-EO-2.0: A versatile multi-temporal foundation model for earth observation applications. *arXiv [cs.CV]*.
- Yang, H. L., M. Laverdiere, T. Hauser, B. Swan, E. Schmidt, J. Moehl, A. Reith, D. Adams, B. Morris, J. McKee, M. Whitehead, and M. Tuttle (2024, May). A baseline structure inventory with critical attribution for the US and its territories. *Sci. Data* 11(1), 502.
- Yuan, M. and A. McKee (2022, July). Embedding scale: new thinking of scale in machine learning and geographic representation. *J. Geogr. Syst.* 24(3), 501–524.